

π , φ and e between Khufu and Khafre

Ian Douglas, B.Sc

ian@zti.co.za

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8452-7111>

27 March 2022

Version 1.0.0

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.6387552](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6387552)

Please check via DOI for latest version.

Unqid: [e1dc0d5b0a213783f9460e0ae2f8729e](https://nqn.zti.co.za/e1dc0d5b0a213783f9460e0ae2f8729e)

Licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

Abstract

Diagrams and calculations showing how the dimensions and relative locations of the Khufu and Khafre pyramids provide reasonable approximations for π , φ , and e . The pyramid sizes and spacing meets other criteria, so this is either co-incidental, or the designers showing off.

Keywords: Egyptology, Giza, pyramids, geometry, archaeogeometry, history of mathematics, π , φ , golden ratio.

Best viewed and printed in colour.

Updates:

1.0.0 Initial release.

“The language of Giza is mathematics.”

Robert Bauval

“You will believe.”

The architects of Giza

Approximations for π , φ and e exist between Khufu and Khafre, in the form of line ratios.

Since line ratios are by definition rational, they can only approximate the irrational π , φ and e .

The pyramid sizes and spacing were determined mathematically, see Zep Tepi Mathematics 101 [1] (ZTM) for a discussion. That paper has a proposed blueprint, which designs Giza from scratch, without the current skewness and rotation. Table 1 compares the co-ordinates from Glen Dash and the Giza Plateau Mapping Project (GPMP), and the values from ZTM.

These co-ordinates are the values from the SVG diagrams, at a scale of 1 pixel : 1 metre, and map directly to the system used by GPMP. They're just easier to use. Note that in SVG, the y-axis starts at the top. The points are in x;y order, where x is west – east. Khufu's centre acts as origin.

System	Pyramid	NW	NE	Centre	SW	SE
GPMP	Khufu	2184.6; 84.9	2415; 84.7	2300; 200	2184.9; 315.3	2415.3; 315.1
ZTM	Khufu	2184.808; 84.808	2415.192; 84.808	2300; 200	2184.808; 315.192	2415.192; 315.192
GPMP	Khafre	1858.2; 446.9	2073.5; 446.6	1966; 554.4	1858.6; 662.2	2073.9; 661.9
ZTM	Khafre	1858.605; 446.616	2073.805; 446.616	1966.205; 554.215	1858.605; 661.815	2073.805; 661.815

Table 1: Comparing GPMP and ZTM corners and centres for Khufu and Khafre.

The analysis results are very similar between the two sets of co-ordinates , for example:

GPMP: $BI/BG = 1.61163$

ZTM: $BI/BG = 1.61164$

So I will use the ZTM co-ordinates and avoid debates about where exactly the corners are.

Fig. 1 has the diagram with the needed lines, and labelled points.

Figure 1: Plan of Khufu and Khafre with needed lines and points.

The builders appeared to be happy to use pragmatic approximations for the irrationals, as in Table 2. Accuracy calculations use these values.

Symbol	Name	Approximate / practical value	% Accuracy to true
π	Archimedes' constant	3.1416	99.9998
φ	Golden ratio	1.618 $\varphi + 1 = \varphi^2 = 2.618$	99.9979
e	Euler's number	2.7183	99.9993

Table 2: Pragmatic values for irrationals.

Then we have the following approximations:

Lines	Values	Result	Approximates	Accuracy %
$\frac{BI}{BG}$	$\frac{801.70205}{497.44342}$	1.612	φ	99.63
$\frac{BI}{GI}$	$\frac{801.7020}{304.3382}$	2.634	φ^2	99.39
$\frac{DI}{HI}$	$\frac{475.9789}{152.1691}$	3.128	π	99.57
$\frac{EI}{EK}$	$\frac{655.6954}{402.1763}$	1.630	φ	99.26
$\frac{GJ}{JK}$	$\frac{215.1996}{134.0189}$	1.606	φ	99.26
$\frac{EF}{FL}$	$\frac{571.8925}{182.0665}$	3.141	π	99.98
$\frac{AH}{HL}$	$\frac{517.8133}{164.8499}$	3.141	π	99.98
$\frac{BI}{EM}$	$\frac{801.7020}{295.6906}$	2.711	e	99.73

Table 3: Approximations for π , φ , φ^2 and e between Khufu and Khafre.

Note that EI and GJ cut each other approximately in the golden ratio at point K, and AH and EF cut each other approximately in the π ratio at point L. Beautiful.

13. Bibliography

[1] I. Douglas, 'Zep Tepi Mathematics 101', Zenodo, Jan. 2021. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.4410650.
 [2] rubenbristian.com, 'Location, Location, Location: Where, Precisely, are the Three Pyramids of Giza? | Glen Dash Foundation for Archaeological Research'.
<http://glendash.com/blog/2014/02/13/location-location-location-where-precisely-are-the-three-pyramids-of-giza/> (accessed Jun. 03, 2019).